

ODISSEI - CBS variable mapping information

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The variable metadata block

In order to map the variable information from the CBS records, we have created a custom metadata block for the ODISSEI portal. This block is called 'Variable Information'. The logic of this metadata block is taken from the [DDI 3.0 Lifecycle metadata standard](#), because the elements in the Dataverse Citation block and the default Social Science metadata block are also based on DDI. We chose for the DDI Lifecycle instead of DDI Codebook, because the CBS metadata was more similar to the DDI Lifecycle standard.

Mapping the CBS variable information to the DDI fields

Note that in the CBS records, they have a 'variable' and a 'contextvariable' (in Dutch), whereas in DDI, you have a variable and a conceptual variable. They are mapped as follows:

CBS	DDI
Contextvariabele	Variable
Variabele	Conceptual variable

A **conceptual variable** can be used to describe many variables free from the context of a dataset. On the other hand, **variable** is used within the context of the dataset. For example, you can define a conceptual variable 'Age', and within a dataset you have the variable 'person's age' and 'mother's age'.

See also this example from the ODISSEI Portal; [this CBS dataset](#) contains a **variable** with the name 'SVOAFLftOP' (Schoolverlatersonderzoek/afleiding/leeftijd op), and variable label 'Leeftijd OP (enquetdatum)'. The corresponding **Conceptual Variable** is

'Leeftijd persoon'.

The table below gives an overview of the metadata fields relating to variable information in the CBS records, and the corresponding fields in the ODISSEI Portal. The last two columns indicate the DDI equivalent field and its description (if applicable).

CBS Field	CBS XPath	Maps to this field in the ODISSEI Portal	ODISSEI Portal internal field description	Related to this DDI field	DDI field description
Context-variabele	Dataontwerpv ersies/Versie/ Dataontwerp/ Contextvariab elen/Contextv ariabele/	Variable (parent field, only the child fields have a value)	This element describes all of the features of a single (conceptual) variable in a social science data file.	Variable	Describes the structure of a Variable. This is the applied expression of a data item within a data set and maps to the GSIM ImplementedVariable. In addition to the standard name, label, and description, includes a reference to a source parameter, represented variable, conceptual variable, universe, concept, question, source variable, and embargo information. It identifies the normal source of the data in the variable, the unit of analysis, whether the variable provides temporal or geographic information, or serves as a weight for other variables in the data, and provides a full description of its representation.
Verkorte schrijfwijze naam variabele	Dataontwerpv ersies/Versie/ Dataontwerp/ Contextvariab elen/Contextv ariabele/Verko rteSchrijfwijze NaamVariabel e	Name	Name of the variable.	Variable.Variable Name	A name for the Variable. May be expressed in multiple languages. Repeat the element to express names with different content, for example different names for different systems.

Label van de variabele	Dataontwerpv ersies/Versie/ Dataontwerp/ Contextvariab elen/Contextv ariabele/Label VanDeVariabel e	Label	Short description of the variable.	Variable.Label	A display label for the Variable. Supports multiple language versions of the same content as well as optional formatting of the content. Repeat for labels with different content, for example, labels with differing length limitations.
Toelichting bij de definitie	Dataontwerpv ersies/Versie/ Dataontwerp/ Contextvariab elen/Contextv ariabele/Toelic htingBijDeDefi nitie	Definition	Extra information related to the definition of the variable.	Variable.Descript ion	A description of the content and purpose of the Variable. Supports multiple language versions of the same content as well as optional formatting of the content.
-	(CBS only uses an ID for the conceptual variable)	ID	Id to uniquely identify the variable.	variable.ID	-
Datatype	Dataontwerpv ersies/Versie/ Dataontwerp/ Contextvariab elen/Contextv ariabele/Datat ype	Data type	Data type of the variable.	None	-

Toelichting bij het gebruik	Dataontwerpv ersies/Versie/ Dataontwerp/ Contextvariab elen/Contextv ariabele/Toelic htingBijHetGe bruik	Processing instruction	Information about how the variable was processed.	Variable.Variable Representation. ProcessingInstru ction	A reference to either a general or generation instruction that was provided to those who converted information from one form to another to create a particular variable. This might include the reordering of numeric information into another form or the conversion of textual information into numeric information. TypeOfObject should be set to GeneralInstruction or GenerationInstruction.
Unieke naam	Dataontwerpver sies/Versie/Data ontwerp/Context variabelen/Cont extvariabele/Vari abele/UniekeNa am	Conceptual Variable Name	Name of the conceptual variable.	ConceptualVaria ble.Name	A name for the ConceptualVariable. May be expressed in multiple languages. Repeat the element to express names with different content, for example different names for different systems.
Definitie	Dataontwerpver sies/Versie/Data ontwerp/Context variabelen/Cont extvariabele/Vari abele/Definitie	Conceptual Variable Definition	The definition of the conceptual variable.	ConceptualVaria ble.Description	A description of the content and purpose of the ConceptualVariable. Supports multiple language versions of the same content as well as optional formatting of the content.
ID	Dataontwerpver sies/Versie/Data ontwerp/Context variabelen/Cont extvariabele/Vari abele/Id	Conceptual Variable ID	The ID of the conceptual variable.	ConceptualVaria ble.ID	-

Objecttype naam	Dataontwerpversies/Versie/Dataontwerp/Contextvariabelen/Contextvariabele/variabele/Variabele Objecttypenaam	Conceptual Variable Object Type	The related object type for the conceptual variable.	ConceptualVariable.UnitType.TypeOfObject	A Unit Type is a class of objects of interest. A Unit Type is used to describe a class or group of Units based on a single characteristic with no specification of time and geography. For example, the Unit Type of "Person" groups together a set of Units based on the characteristic that they are "Persons".
Geldig vanaf	Dataontwerpversies/Versie/Dataontwerp/Contextvariabelen/Contextvariabele/Variabele/GeldigVanaf	Conceptual Variable Valid from	Valid from date provided by the metadata distributor.	ConceptualVariable.VersionDate	Date of version using the union set BaseType. Duration should not be used in this field, even though allowed by the ISO format enforced by the parser.
Versie	Dataontwerpversies/Versie/Dataontwerp/Contextvariabelen/Contextvariabele/Variabele/Versie	Conceptual Variable Version	Version number of the conceptual variable provided by the metadata distributor.	ConceptualVariable.Version	-
Eigenaar	Dataontwerpversies/Versie/Dataontwerp/Contextvariabelen/Contextvariabele/variabele/Eigenaar	Conceptual Variable Version Responsibility	Person or organization responsible for the version change.	ConceptualVariable.VersionResponsibility	Person or organization within the MaintenanceAgency responsible for the version change. If it is important to retain the affiliation between and individual responsible for the version and his/her agency, it may be included in this notation. This is primarily

					intended for internal use.
Thema	Dataontwerpversies/Versie/Dataontwerp/Contextvariabelen/Contextvariabele/Variabele/Themas/Thema	Topic	Topic indicated by CBS.	None	
Trefwoord	Dataontwerpversies/Versie/Dataontwerp/Contextvariabelen/Contextvariabele/Trefwoorden/Trefwoord	Keyword	Keyword as indicated by CBS.	None	
Variabelengroep	Dataontwerpversies/Versie/Dataontwerp/Contextvariabelen/Contextvariabele/Variabele/Variabelengroep	Variable group path	Variable group path indicated by CBS.	None	
Waardestelselnaam	Dataontwerpversies/Versie/Dataontwerp/Contextvariabelen/Contextvariabele/variabele/Waardestelselnaam	Value system name	Value system name indicated by CBS.	None	

Volgnummer	Dataontwerpversies/Versie/Dataontwerp/Contextvariabelen/Contextvariabele/Volgnummer	Reference Number	Reference number as indicated by CBS.	none	
None		Vocabulary URI	Vocabulary URI for the variable.	none	